

SOFTWARE TOOL ARTICLE

WALIS dashboard: An online tool to explore a global paleo sea-level database [version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]

Sebastián Garzón¹, Alessio Rovere^{2,3}

¹Laboratory of Geo-information Science and Remote Sensing, Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, Gelderland, 6708PB, The Netherlands

²Department of Environmental Sciences, Informatics and Statistics, Università Ca' Foscari, Venice, 30172, Italy

³MARUM, Center for Marine Environmental Sciences, University of Bremen, Bremen, 28359, Germany

V1 First published: 14 Jul 2023, 3:114
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16183.1>
 Latest published: 01 Mar 2024, 3:114
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16183.2>

Abstract

This paper describes the WALIS dashboard, an open-access interface to the World Atlas of Last Interglacial Shorelines (WALIS), which was developed and compiled thanks to funding from the European Research Council. WALIS is a database that includes thousands of samples (dated with different radiometric methods) and sea-level indicators formed during the Last Interglacial (125 ka). The WALIS dashboard was coded in R (shiny app) and is connected with a simplified version of the WALIS database. The app allows querying data by geographic extent or by filtering metadata. It then allows the user to download the queried data and perform simple reproducible data analysis. The WALIS dashboard can be used both online and offline.

Keywords

Past sea level change, Geological database, Last Interglacial, Data visualisation, Sea-level changes, Paleoclimate

This article is included in the [European Research Council \(ERC\) gateway](#).

This article is included in the [Horizon Europe gateway](#).

Open Peer Review

Approval Status ? ✓

	1	2
version 2 (revision) 01 Mar 2024		✓ view
version 1 14 Jul 2023	? view	? view

1. **Schmitty B. Thompson**, Oregon State University, Corvallis, USA

Jessica R. Creveling, Oregon State University, Corvallis, USA

2. **Jennifer S. Walker** , Rowan University, Glassboro, USA

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

This article is included in the [Earth and Environmental Sciences gateway](#).

Corresponding author: Sebastián Garzón (j.s.garzonavarado@uu.nl)

Author roles: **Garzón S:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation;

Rovere A: Conceptualization, Funding Acquisition, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme (Grant agreement No. 802414). Sebastián Garzón was also funded by the Data Stewardship Scholarship (DSS-107), by PAGES - Past Global Changes - (which in turn received support from the Swiss Academy of Sciences and the Chinese Academy of Sciences).

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Copyright: © 2023 Garzón S and Rovere A. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

How to cite this article: Garzón S and Rovere A. **WALIS dashboard: An online tool to explore a global paleo sea-level database [version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]** Open Research Europe 2023, 3:114 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16183.1>

First published: 14 Jul 2023, 3:114 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16183.1>

Plain language summary

Tide gauges and satellites provide reliable measurements of sea-level changes since the beginning of the 20th century. To estimate sea-level changes before this period, we rely on sea-level indicators, i.e., geological features that were formed in close connection with sea level in the past, such as fossil shallow-water coral reefs or cemented beach deposits. Similar to tide gauge and satellite data, data on sea-level indicators are collected and standardised in databases, which are then made available to the scientific community (and the public at large) for further analysis. In this work, we present an open-source application that allows exploring, analysing, and downloading sea-level indicators included in the World Atlas of Last Interglacial Shorelines (WALIS), a paleo sea-level database compiled thanks to funding from the European Research Council. The application aims to facilitate access to this information for researchers, students, and citizens by creating more interactive and intuitive ways to explore scientific information.

Introduction

Geological indicators of past sea levels are fundamental to assess how ice sheets melted in the past and provide fundamental benchmarks to define possible scenarios of ice sheets melting in a warmer future climate¹. To be used as a sea-level indicator (or “sea level index point”) a geological feature must be assigned an elevation and geographic location, an age via radiometric methods or stratigraphic correlation, and must have a quantifiable relationship with a former sea level². Knowing these three parameters allows for reconstructing the elevation of the relative sea-level at a point in time in the past. After correction for land motions (e.g., tectonics, or glacial isostatic adjustment³), it is possible to reconstruct the global mean sea level at the time the sea-level indicator was formed.

The advent of data digitalisation has provided paleo sea-level researchers with new opportunities to discover and access studies from different research groups. Among the tools facilitating the exchange of information, scientific articles and open-access repositories have opened the possibility to download and analyse sea-level data to anyone with internet access. However, access to new studies and data comes with additional challenges for researchers. A widespread challenge is that the information related to sea-level indicators is communicated in multiple ways (e.g., graphs, tables, in-text explanations, supplementary information) that require readers to navigate between different styles and conventions. Sea level researchers often face additional challenges as a correct interpretation of data requires an understanding of several measurement and dating techniques, and requires in-depth knowledge of how the original information (e.g. stratigraphic context of geological sea-level index points) was interpreted by the authors. Recent standardisation efforts among the sea-level research community have resulted in standardised formats designed to store and share sea-level indicators in a way that allows different researchers to understand the origin and details of their measurements and reproduce the process to extract their components^{4,5}. *The World Atlas of Last Interglacial Shorelines* (WALIS) is a standardised

database that includes data from thousands of studies since the early 1900s. The focus is on sea-level indicators formed during marine isotope stage 5 (MIS 5)⁶. The database includes 4545 sea-level proxies and 4110 dated samples standardised from 2130 references compiled by multiple research groups within a special issue of the Earth System Science Data (ESSD) journal. The structure of the database consists of multiple tables with one-to-one or many-to-many relationships that are openly available in Zenodo⁷ in different export formats (e.g., CSV and geoJSON). In this work, we present an online dashboard that allows exploring WALIS data without having to download the database and with no coding knowledge required.

WALIS Dashboard

The main purpose of the WALIS Dashboard is to provide an alternative entry point for users to explore the WALIS database information (WALIS is licensed under CC-BY 4 and our use falls within the extent of this license). [Figure 1](#) shows how the dashboard serves as a connection point between data creators, data compilers, external contributors, and end-users around the WALIS database. Traditional access for end-users of WALIS would require them to directly download the full dataset from Zenodo. Given the complexity required to standardise sea level indicators, these tasks would require users to familiarise themselves with the dataset structure before exploring the content. Similarly, end-users would need to develop their own data visualisation methods to find relevant information in the dataset. Given the challenges that might discourage or make dataset exploring difficult, the WALIS dashboard provides an alternative path for a user to easily get an idea of the content of the dataset provided by the data creators and data compiler. Additionally, the dashboard integrates external contributions from researchers to explore the content of WALIS within a selected region of interest. All relevant documentation are provided in *Underlying data*⁸ and *Software availability*⁹.

Implementation

The WALIS Dashboard is an interactive application developed using open-source R packages. The application is built using the R-Shiny package (RRID:SCR_001626)¹⁰ that allows integration of data and analysis in an interactive web platform. The application includes individual data visualisations often used in the literature to provide context about sea-level indicators such as maps, sea-level plots, and tables. Additionally, the application allows users to apply a Monte Carlo method proposed by [11](#) to merge and summarise multiple sea-level indicators using the WALIS database structure.

To display this information the application is divided into three tabs: (1) Interactive map, (2) Summary table, and (3) Merge SLIP. These are briefly described below.

Interactive map

The interactive map tab integrates filtering options of the data set, a map visualisation, and a sea-level plot ([Figure 2](#)). In our design, we maintain important elements of the structure of the data set regarding both measurement and interpretation of the data as proposed by [4](#).

Figure 1. WALIS Dashboard diagram.

Figure 2. Interactive map tab showing a selection of sea-level indicators in Curaçao and Bonaire.

The filtering option (Figure 3) allows selecting by type of indicator (i.e., Sea-level index point or limiting data) and allows culling the selection by age, relative sea-level (RSL), and location using other panels and elements as input. The “Age filter menu” (Figure 3a) allows users to trim the data by timeframe of interest, age uncertainty, and dating techniques. The “RSL Indicator filter” (Figure 3b) allows instead to selection of sea-level indicators by type, elevation error, paleo-RSL percentiles, and Uncertainty. The WALIS Dashboard also allows resampling

the database by Geographic extent (Figure 3c), showing information only within a particular area of interest. Via this interface, the user can either select data in the current map area or draw an area of interest.

Based on the filters applied to the data, the map visualisation displays the sea-level indicators with pop-ups with additional information. These include data and metadata on elevation measurements and dating, interpretation, and literature references.

Figure 3. WALIS dashboard filters.

The sea-level plot is the main element of data visualisation in the “Interactive map” tab. Based on the filters applied to the data, a graph is updated in real-time, displaying sea-level indicators in a sea-level vs time plot. In the graph, we implemented a symbology for the nine types of sea-level indicators and associated ages resulting from the WALIS structure. These new symbols represent particular cases of the three main types of indicators: Sea-level index points (SLIP), terrestrial limiting, and marine limiting. The platform includes details for all nine types of indicators clarifying their meaning for the temporal and relative-sea level dimensions.

Summary table

The “Summary table” tab includes the information on the data as filtered in the “Interactive map” tab. As a visual guide, this tab displays the current filters and a map with the area of interest. The table includes additional information on the sea-level indicators and allows users to explore the content before using the export options available in the application. Additionally, users can download the summary table from this tab in CSV format. Figure 4 shows the summary table tab showing a selection of sea-level indicators in Curaçao and Bonaire.

Merge SLIP

The “Merge SLIP” tab allows the user to create a point cloud of Relative Sea-level (RSL) and Age values with the sea-level index points that were selected in the “Interactive map” tab (Figure 5). The merging method follows the methodology proposed by 11 to combine the different probability distributions of Age and RSL values of each sea-level index point (SLIP) into a single point cloud. Before merging the data, the user can further filter the dataset, modify the sampling strategy, and determine the number of points to be sampled.

After the sea level index points are merged, the user can explore the results in a sea level vs age plot. The results can then be exported using two different strategies: Point cloud download or Docker container. The first option exports the resulting point cloud into a CSV file accompanied by a geoJSON file with information about the filters used to extract the selection of data. The second option creates a docker image accompanied by the required data and code to fully reproduce the results of the data merging. Therefore results obtained remotely in the Dashboard are fully reproducible on a local machine.

Figure 4. Summary table tab showing a selection of sea-level indicators in Curaçao and Bonaire.

Figure 5. Merge SLIPs (Sea Level Index Points) tabs showing data selection in Curaçao and Bonaire.

Operation

System requirements

The WALIS dashboard can be accessed both online and offline. The online version is available as a shiny app [here](#) (Last access July 3, 2023). The target for the online app is users that need to explore the WALIS data set

(e.g., sea-level researchers, students). Users do not need to install any R package or manipulate any code. Access to the online version only requires a stable internet connection. The dashboard can be accessed in a local build after downloading the source code available on our [GitHub repository](#) or in the Zenodo repository⁹. The software was

developed using R (RRID:SCR_001905) version 4.1.0¹². The target for the offline version is researchers that want to contribute to expanding the capabilities of the dashboard. Contributions are welcome as new issues or pull requests in the main GitHub repository.

Local shiny application

Users can deploy a local implementation of the shiny application using the {renv} package. This option provides the required files and R packages information. An R installation is a prerequisite for this option.

1. Download the WALIS dashboard from GitHub - see *Software availability*⁹

2. Open R and install the *renv* package.

```
install.package("renv")
```

3. Open the R Project file (WALIS_Visualization.Rproj). This file should start the process to restore the dependencies of the project using the Lockfile (renv.lock). You can manually restore the dependencies using the function `restore()` from the R package *renv*

```
library("renv")
restore(renv.lock)
```

4. Open the app.R file.

5. Run the App using the `runApp()` function from the Shiny R package.

```
library("shiny")
runApp(your_path/to/app.R)
```

Docker image

A Docker image to run the application is available as part of the application. This docker image allows the application to be fully reproducible as the instructions and computational requirements (e.g., operating system, R packages) to deploy the application inside a software container are automated. The only prerequisite is to have Docker (see 13) installed and running on the local machine. This option is mostly available to guarantee the reproducibility of the application in the long term.

Download and start-up instructions - Docker

1. Download the WALIS dashboard from GitHub - see *Software availability*⁹

2. Open Docker to run in the background

3. Open a terminal and access the folder with the application

```
cd WALIS_Visualization
```

4. Create a Docker container using the Dockerfile image. This process could take hours the first time as it requires setting up all computational requirements.

```
docker build -t 'walis-shiny'.
```

5. Run the Docker container

```
docker run -p 3838:3838 'walis-shiny'
```

6. Open the application in a web browser at <http://localhost:3838>

Use cases

Use case #1: Discovering sea level indicators

This use case illustrates the most common use of the tool to discover sea-level indicators in an area during a specific time period. In this case, we illustrate how a researcher can find sea-level indicators under multiple restrictions:

1. Only Sea Level Index Points (SLIPs)
2. SLIPs around the Last Interglacial (130.000 to 115.000 ka).
3. SLIPs dated using Uranium-Thorium (U-Series) dating.
4. SLIPs located in Bonaire and the Northern Part of Curaçao
5. SLIPs with elevation measurement errors below 10 meters.

Figure 6a shows the filter configuration required to select sea level indicators under the conditions. First, the user can exclude Marine Limiting and Terrestrial Limiting indicators using the “Indicator type” menu located on the Map. Second, in the Age filter menu, the user can select the desired period around the Last Interglacial (e.g., 135 to 110 ka to include additional data) by modifying the Age range slider. In this menu, the user can exclude other dating techniques (e.g., Amino acid racemisation -AAR- and Luminescence) by clicking on them. Third, in the RSL Indicator filter user can modify the elevation error slider to only include the range between 0 and 10 meters. Finally, the user should enable the “From polygon (draw)” option in the Geographic extent filter menu. After enabling this option, the user can draw a polygon that excludes the southern part of Curaçao (Figure 6b).

Multiple observations can be made after data selection. For example, there are 21 sea-level indicators (e.g., *RSL_3559* and *RSL_3553*) with a total of 48 individual constraints in the area. Taking all individual constraints into account, the sea level plot shows that the relative sea level during the Last Interglacial in this area fluctuated between 2.5 and 20 meters. A rapid scan using the Summary Table tab shows that relevant literature for the search includes, among other five articles, 14 and 15. A summary of these newly discovered sea-level indicators under a series of specific conditions can be downloaded for further inspection using the download menu available both in the Interactive Map and Summary Table tabs. The *WALIS_ID* field from all sea-level indicators found in the search will enable users after downloading the full WALIS database to easily identify sea levels in this area.

Use case #2: Estimating relative sea level

Using the selection of sea-level indicators from the previous use case we can estimate the relative sea-level in this area. As

(a) Filters

(b) Map visualisation

(c) Sea level plot

Figure 6. Use case 1: Discovering sea level indicators.

relative sea-level indicators can have more than one constraint, analysing the sea level plot from Use case #1 might not be sufficient to estimate the sea level in the area. For example, in our selection, there are sea-level indicators with five individual constraints. In the sea-level plot, this would result in five more relative sea level (RSL) points (i.e., symbols in the plot) than a sea-level indicator with only one constraint. Therefore, for estimating RSL our strategy is to merge individual constraints and compare only the final sea-level indicators using the methodology proposed by 11. This methodology summarises sea level indicators by creating a point cloud based on individual constraints. All sea level indicators have the same final number of points no matter the initial number of constraints per indicator.

Users can create a point cloud of relative sea level values using the Merging SLIP tab. Figure 7 shows the filtering and merging options required to estimate the relative sea level for this area based on the selection. First, the user selects a sampling strategy among two possible options proposed by 11: Regular sampling and Peak sampling. Generally, Regular sampling is the default merging strategy while Peak sampling is only relevant for sea level indicators with uniform temporal constraints. For example, sea level indicators in which the age calculation comes from a Uniform distribution from a Marine Isotope Stage (MIS) assignment. Second, the user can use the

SLIPs filter to remove individual sea-level indicators by code if required. Finally, the user can select the number of points per sea-level indicator. The upper limit of 10.000 points per indicator is set to not overload the application with calculations.

After processing, the user can see the relative sea level point cloud (Figure 7) and include a density calculation. Based on the selected data, we can estimate that around 130 and 125 ka relative sea level in Bonaire and the Northern Part of Curaçao was around 12 and 5 m with a decreasing tendency. Both the sea level plot and the point cloud can be downloaded using the Download menu.

Use case #3: Reproducing the results

The analysis performed in Use Case #2 can be extended if combined with other sources of sea level information. For example, RSL point clouds can be combined with Global Isostatic Adjustment (GIA) models from the area as described by 11. For these additional analyses, it is important to keep track of the origin of the point clouds and how this source of sea level information was obtained.

A folder with all required information is available to guarantee that any analysis performed in the dashboard can be reproduced outside the application (Figure 8). This folder includes

Merging Options

Filtering and merging options

Define the merging parameters and filter the SLIPs by WALIS ID to generate the point cloud. Once you are ready, press ▶ Start merging

Sampling strategy
Regular sampler

SLIPs filter
USeries_1763, l

Points per SLIP
100

▶ Start merging

Download menu

You can directly download the point cloud in a file or a docker container. The docker container allows you to reproduce the result in your computer.

Point cloud Docker container

Relative Sea level point cloud

Figure 7. Use case 2: Merging Sea level indicators.

```

.
├── Data
│   ├── sea_level_stack_spratt.csv
│   └── walis_merging.csv
├── Dockerfile
├── r
│   ├── define_peaks_ranges.R
│   ├── extract_age.R
│   ├── extract_rsl.R
│   ├── join_age_rsl.R
│   └── run_analysis.R
├── readme_container.md
├── renv.lock
└── spratt2016stack.bib

```

Figure 8. Use case 3: Tree structure docker container folder.

a *Data* subfolder with all SLIP in the area in CSV format, an *R* subfolder with all scripts required to perform an analysis, a *renv.lock* file to keep track of all required R-packages, a *Dockerfile* to generate the container, and a *readme_container.md* file with detailed instructions on how to reproduce the analysis. To reproduce the results of the analysis and generate the same point cloud as in the dashboard, users need to follow these instructions:

1. Download the Docker container in the Download menu
2. Open Docker to run in the background
3. Open a terminal and access the folder

```
cd WALIS_docker
```

4. Create a Docker container using the Dockerfile image. This process could take a couple of minutes depending on the characteristics of the local machine.

```
ddocker build -f Dockerfile_container -t 'walis-ok'.
```

5. Run the Docker container

```
docker run -p 80:80 walis-ok
```

6. To extract the result from the container (CSV file with point clouds) users need to transfer the file from the container to their local machine. For this, users need to identify the CONTAINER_ID.

```
docker ps -a
```

- Using the 10-character {CONTAINER ID} string users can now transfer the file to their local machines.

```
docker cp {CONTAINER ID}:/merging/
pointcloud_output.csv.
```

- The pointcloud_output.csv file will be available now in the WALIS_docker folder

In addition to reproducing the analysis performed using the dashboard, the content of this folder provides the user with all the required information to perform their own individual analysis.

Conclusions

In this article, we present an open-source online dashboard developed using R packages to explore the WALIS database. This dashboard provides an example of how open-source tools can be used to simplify access to database information for research teams with limited software development capabilities. The interactive application consists of three tabs that summarise the database information for researchers to provide a user-friendly point of connection to the information. The application includes basic data processing methods that provide meaningful observations for researchers to start analysing the content of the database. Given the application design, end-users of the application should be able to easily explore the WALIS database before engaging in more complex and time-consuming tasks to understand the database structure. To promote further developments and guarantee the long-term and offline maintenance of the application, the software includes reproducibility strategies such as software containers and dependency management strategies. Similarly, the application is licensed under an MIT permissive free software license to promote researcher teams to implement similar interactive visualisation approaches for other databases.

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

Data availability

Underlying data

Zenodo: WALIS - The World Atlas of Last Interglacial Shorelines (Ver 1.0 final).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7348242>⁸.

This project contains the following underlying data:

- Atlas_Versions/Ver_1/Ver_1_0_post_review/Output/DB_Structure/Summary_full.csv (CSV file containing the WALIS summary table).

Data are available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Public License](#) (CC BY 4.0).

Software availability

Software available from: https://warmcoasts.shinyapps.io/WALIS_Visualization/

Source code available from: https://github.com/Alerovere/WALIS_visualization

Archived source code at time of publication: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8013088>⁹

Licence: [MIT](#)

Acknowledgements

We thank Dr. Kim Cohen for his valuable comments during the development of the visualisation tool.

References

- Golledge NR, Clark PU, He F, *et al.*: **Retreat of the antarctic ice sheet during the last interglaciation and implications for future change.** *Geophys Res Lett.* 2021; **48**(17): e2021GL094513. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Shennan I: **chapter 2, Handbook of sea-level research.** John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2015; 3–25. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Rovere A, Stocchi P, Vacchi M: **Eustatic and relative sea level changes.** *Curr Clim Change Rep.* 2016; **2**: 221–231. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Düsterhus A, Rovere A, Carlson AE, *et al.*: **Palaeo-sea-level and palaeo-ice-sheet databases: problems, strategies, and perspectives.** *Climate of the Past.* 2016; **12**(4): 911–921. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Khan NS, Horton BP, Engelhart S, *et al.*: **Inception of a global atlas of sea levels since the last glacial maximum.** *Quat Sci Rev.* 2019; **220**: 359–371. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Rovere A, Ryan DD, Vacchi M, *et al.*: **The world atlas of last interglacial shorelines (version 1.0).** *Earth Syst Sci Data.* 2023; **15**(1): 1–23. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Rovere A, Ryan DD, Vacchi M, *et al.*: **WALIS - The World Atlas of Last Interglacial Shorelines (Ver 1.0 final).** 2022. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Rovere A, Ryan DD, Vacchi M, *et al.*: **WALIS - The World Atlas of Last Interglacial Shorelines (Ver 1.0 final) (v1.0-final).** Zenodo. [dataset] 2022. <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7348242>
- Garzón S, Rovere A: **Walis_visualization (v3.0).** 2023. <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8013088>
- Chang W, Cheng J, Allaire JJ, *et al.*: **shiny: Web Application Framework for R.** R package version 1.7.4.9002. 2023. [Reference Source](#)
- Garzón S: **A methodology to compare sea-level index points and sea-level models.** Master's thesis, University of Münster, 2020.
- R Core Team: **R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing.** R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria, 2021. [Reference Source](#)
- Merkel D: **Docker: Lightweight linux containers for consistent development and deployment.** *Linux J.* 2014; **2014**(239): 2. [Reference Source](#)
- Muhs DR, Pandolfi JM, Simmons KR, *et al.*: **Sea-level history of past interglacial periods from uranium-series dating of corals, Curaçao, Leeward Antilles islands.** *Quat Res.* 2012; **78**(2): 157–169. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Schellmann G, Radtke U, Scheffers A, *et al.*: **ESR Dating of Coral Reef Terraces on Curaçao (Netherlands Antilles) with Estimates of Younger Pleistocene Sea Level Elevations.** *J Coast Res.* 2004; **2004**(204): 947–957. [Publisher Full Text](#)

Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status: ? ?

Version 1

Reviewer Report 14 September 2023

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.17470.r34623>

© 2023 S. Walker J. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Jennifer S. Walker

Rowan University, Glassboro, New Jersey, USA

This manuscript introduces and details the WALIS dashboard, which is a new interface to explore and interact with sea-level data contained in the World Atlas of Last Interglacial Shorelines paleo sea-level database which has been previously published. The dashboard allows users to quickly explore the available data through a map visualization, sea-level plots, and a series of filters such as the type of indicator, age, or uncertainty. The authors provide their motivation for creating the dashboard and describe how to use the various elements of the interface with detailed examples through three case studies.

An online open-access tool to investigate an extensive standardized sea-level database is very useful within the sea-level community and for anyone interested in simply exploring available sea-level data in an accessible, interactive way. Having such an interface is a great next step forward from the standardized sea-level databases that have been created across different spatial and temporal scales. Overall I would approve this manuscript with reservations considering my comments below.

Comments

In the last paragraph of the introduction, it is not clear what is meant by 'one-to-one and many-to-many relationships.' Could the authors please explain this?

The interactive map and summary table are valuable tools to have and use case #1 clearly describes how to discover sea level indicators in a way that is simple to replicate. However, I am uncertain about the use of the Merge SLIP feature that is described in use case #2. The method is from a masters thesis that does not seem to be available online and is not fully described in this manuscript. I would suggest the methodology be fully presented in this paper to go through formal peer-review or that this feature is removed from the dashboard until the methodology for the Merge SLIP is published elsewhere and could be added to the dashboard at a later date. As written, it is unclear how the Merge SLIP results should be interpreted, if at all, or if this is just another method to simply view a particular dataset. The dashboard is still a valuable tool with the

map, summary, and plotting features to access paleo sea-level data. Further, I was not able to replicate use case #2 because the dashboard crashes when I tried to produce the point cloud and density figures and then resets all of the filters.

Use case #3 describes how to reproduce the results, which is important by itself, but is not really an example of how to use the dashboard, which should require no coding experience as stated in the introduction. I did not try to replicate use case #3 so cannot comment on its reproducibility, but I might suggest moving this information to a supplemental file for those interested where perhaps an example could be included with how users would perform their own individual analyses.

Because the manuscript is focused on the accessibility and exploration of data, and I am not sure about the suitability or relevance of use cases #2 and #3, one suggestion might be to add a new use case #2 that is focused on the dashboard and its specific features. Use case #1 is about discovering sea level indicators, so perhaps the authors could have a use case that begins with more of an actual research question and explore how a user could use the dashboard to determine where data is available, what relevant information is available in the summary table, and how having access to the dashboard specifically contributes to advancing the paleo sea-level field.

While the manuscript is generally clearly written, there is some awkward wording throughout the text, including typos/misspelled words in the text and within the figures (ex. 'analyse' spelled incorrectly in Figure 1), the capitalization of words or terms from the dashboard is inconsistent (ex. sometimes only first word of a term is capitalized, other times all words are capitalized – see 'Age filter' and 'RSL Indicator filter' on page 4), and some unnecessary/repetitive wording or descriptions. Overall the text could be cleaner and would benefit from a readthrough to correct these mistakes and inconsistencies.

The interface itself is straightforward to use, but would benefit from final editing to fix typos and inconsistent capitalization of categories and terms throughout the various menus to improve the clarity of the dashboard.

Another comment with the dashboard is that if you move to another window or other internet tab for a period of time, the dashboard will often 'disconnect from the server', so that when you go back to the dashboard, anything you were previously viewing has been reset and you would have to start over with finding data, setting filters, etc.

Answers to peer review form questions

Is the rationale for developing the new software tool clearly explained?

- Yes, the rationale is clearly explained in the introduction and its benefits to the scientific community are outlined in the intro and reiterated in the conclusions. Having this dashboard greatly simplifies accessing and visualizing available data as is described in the manuscript.

Is the description of the software tool technically sound?

- Yes, the descriptions of the software to use the dashboard and the offline version are clear and detailed. However, I did not access the offline version.

Are sufficient details of the code, methods and analysis (if applicable) provided to allow replication

of the software development and its use by others?

- Partly; the code is available on Github and provides opportunities for replication, as well as through the offline version of the software. However, as stated above, I could not fully replicate use case #2 as the online dashboard kept crashing when I tried to produce the point cloud and density figures. Further, the methods for the Merge SLIP feature are not publicly available and should either be incorporated into this manuscript or the Merge SLIP feature should be removed from the dashboard.

Is sufficient information provided to allow interpretation of the expected output datasets and any results generated using the tool?

- Partly; the interactive map and summary table features produce expected results that can be easily interpreted and are the most valuable part of the dashboard. The manuscript does not provide sufficient information to interpret the Merge SLIP feature as the methods are not described fully or available elsewhere. In the current state of the manuscript and dashboard, the Merge SLIP feature could potentially result in misinterpretation of sea-level data from users since the methods and output are not fully explained.

Is the rationale for developing the new software tool clearly explained?

Yes

Is the description of the software tool technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of the code, methods and analysis (if applicable) provided to allow replication of the software development and its use by others?

Partly

Is sufficient information provided to allow interpretation of the expected output datasets and any results generated using the tool?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Paleo sea level reconstructions/modeling

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Reviewer Report 31 August 2023

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.17470.r33941>

© 2023 R. Creveling J et al. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Schmitty B. Thompson

Oregon State University, Corvallis, Oregon, USA

Jessica R. Creveling

Oregon State University, Corvallis, Oregon, USA

Summary of the Article's Contribution to the Scientific Community

In the article titled 'WALIS dashboard: An online tool to explore a global paleo sea-level database', authors Garzón and Rovere present a dashboard or 'graphical user interface' that enables users with little or no coding knowledge to query the World Atlas of Last Interglacial Shorelines (WALIS) (see Rovere *et al.*, *ESSD*, 2023). The authors present the rationale for this dashboard, a text description of the visualization (map view, table view), and describe research analysis capabilities within this dashboard using three case studies.

The following comments arise from two co-reviewers' (Creveling, Thompson) exploration of the online version of the WALIS dashboard; neither of us accessed the offline version through the downloads described in the Operation section and, hence, cannot speak to that functionality.

Creveling's Overarching Comments

I offer high praise of the interactive map and the summary table components of the WALIS Dashboard. The Interactive Map is a tremendous tool to achieve the goal of case study #1, to discover sea level indicators. The Summary table is a complementary companion to the map-view, and this table guides users into the underlying data/the scientific literature. Overall, the map and table are accessible and easy to navigate. While I offer minor critique on how to enhance these features in the dashboard functionality comments below, I feel that these contributions are ready to share with the community.

My broader criticisms relate to user case studies #2 and #3.

For case study #2, the user is guided towards creating a point-cloud of relative sea-level change based using the Merge SLIP tab, and from this encouraged to make research-relevant conclusions, such as "around 130 and 125 ka relative sea level in Bonaire and the northern part of Curaçao was around 12 and 5 m, with a decreasing tendency." First, I have concerns that the MergeSLIP method does not appear to be peer reviewed--the reference for this is a Master's thesis that was not accessible in my internet search. While I do not assume that the output is inaccurate, I simply note that it is not evaluable with the given information. I have reservations about the precedent of releasing an unevaluated output to a user community that may lack sea level expertise. Second, I ask that the authors provide a specific, nuanced definition of 'relative sea level' in the context of the underlying WALIS data. The example sea level conclusion presented by the authors, that relative sea level was around 12 and 5 m, will likely be perceived very differently based upon expertise. I illustrate this with an example from our own WALIS database entries. If one looked at the 'relative sea level' at Newport, Oregon, during MIS 5a (~80 ka), one sees a paleo-RSL of 22.11 m \pm 23.04 m. Yet this does not mean that sea level fluctuated between -1 and 45 m at Newport, Oregon during MIS 5a--instead, this is a range that reflects the present-day terrace elevation from 22.5 m \pm 22.74 m arising from tectonic warping of the marine terrace over space (the source publication reports this terrace between ~0 - 45 m modern elevation). This "relative sea level" takes no account of regional tectonic uplift. (Perhaps we erred in how we have input this data, leading to this confusion? If so, perhaps others have too?) So it's from this perspective that when I

read in Case study #1 that the authors state that “the sea level plot shows that the relative sea level during the Last Interglacial in this area fluctuated between 2.5 and 20 meters.” that I find myself in disagreement. Have the authors defined ‘relative sea level’ as how the height of the ocean (the geoid) rises relative to the land, and included in that definition land motion from tectonic deformation that accrued long after the indicator formed? The authors state in the Introduction paragraph that corrections for land motions are crucial for global mean sea level—yet I contend that they are crucial for local relative sea level too. Thus, defining “relative sea level” with respect to the WALIS input data is crucial to prevent non-experts from misinterpreting or over-interpret the output.

Case study #3 (Reproducing the results) shares with users how to reproduce the SLIP Merge analysis presented in case study #2, though this appears to require coding skills more advanced than ‘no coding knowledge’. Whether this remains in the manuscript will depend on the justification for the non-peer reviewed SLIPMerge method. Should it stay, I ask the authors to clarify the first paragraph of this subsection (page 8). I was left with ambiguity about whether this code simply reproduces the relative sea level point cloud in Figure 7 (case study #2) or whether it applies a GIA correction to this point cloud. Please clarify.

In summary I recommend that the article be revised to: (i) offer clear explanation for how to interpret “relative sea level”, the measure in the sea level plot, given the nature of the underlying WALIS data, and (ii) either eliminate the filtering/merging that generates the relative sea level point cloud or greatly expand the methodological description so that this analysis can be thoroughly peer reviewed. For request (ii) my strong preference would be to ask the authors to separate these two components into distinct publications (removing the point cloud from the Dashboard publication), and then to incorporate the relative sea level point cloud (all ‘analysis’ tools) into the Dashboard after peer review.

Thompson’s Overarching Comments

The problem of effectively accessing and utilizing paleo-shoreline data is well known to the community, and the WALIS interface described in this publication is a strong step towards increasing data accessibility. The authors successfully introduce the issue at hand and present the WALIS dashboard as a solution to improve data accessibility.

My first broad comment is how the manuscript reports the span and utility of the database. The article abstract presents the contents of the database as “indicators formed during the Last Interglacial (125 ka)” while the database itself contains indicators ranging in age from up to ~450 kyr ago to near present day. Though the project presents itself as the “Atlas of Last Interglacial Shorelines”, the data contained in the database which falls outside of strict last interglacial (LIG) bounds is an important resource. Literature introducing the database to the public shouldn’t exclude components which may be important to those working outside of the LIG. A brief discussion of the scope of data included which falls outside of the LIG will help researchers interested in a wider temporal span utilize the database. Additionally, it is worth mentioning in the introduction that much of the shoreline data is applicable to fields outside of sea level research, such as active tectonics and archeology. Acknowledging a wider range of fields when introducing the database will help broaden the audience for this manuscript (and the database itself).

I also support the point made above in Creveling’s Overarching Comments that presenting paleo-shoreline elevations as “relative sea level” misses important nuance in interpreting relative sea

level data. On many coastlines, especially those near active margins, tectonic movement may lead to significant displacement, sometimes shifting indicators upwards of ~100 m vertically during the interval between the LIG and present day. Interpreting relative sea level from these indicators requires careful correction to remove the tectonic signal, which can significantly obscure the record of sea level change. I appreciate the authors acknowledgement of the role of tectonics and GIA in interpreting global mean sea level from an indicator, but both of these factors also play a large role in interpreting local shoreline data.

Overall, the WALIS dashboard is a valuable contribution to the sea level community and I appreciate the authors efforts to give an overview in this manuscript. Revisions to address the scope of the data presented in the manuscript and careful reconsideration of the way case study #2 presents the interpretation of sea level data would improve the manuscript.

Response to Open Research Europe's guiding review questions

Is the rationale for developing the new software tool clearly explained?

The authors adequately lay out the importance of an interface for the WALIS database as an easy-to-use tool for researchers interested in utilizing (particularly a portion of) the compiled sea level data. As these reviewers are well familiar with, accessing sea level data through the primary publications can be a frustrating endeavor due to inconsistent reporting and standardization, and through the introduction, dashboard overview, and case study #1, the authors make a strong case for how their interactive interface will benefit the greater sea level community.

Is the description of the software tool technically sound?

The authors provide adequate detail of the technical base for the dashboard, supported by providing the full source code powering the dashboard through GitHub and an archived version on Zenodo. As neither reviewer accessed the offline versions of the database, we are not able to speak to the technical descriptions of the offline versions.

Are sufficient details of the code, methods and analysis (if applicable) provided to allow replication of the software development and its use by others?

The base code powering the dashboard itself, being accessible through GitHub and an archived version on Zenodo provides the basis for replicability. The manuscript provides instructions for replicating the full software offline through R and Docker, though neither of us tested these cases. Case study #1 is mostly replicable in the online version, other than some inconsistencies in the parameters outlined in the text (see Line-Specific Comments below for details). Neither reviewer was able to fully replicate case study #2 as displayed in the manuscript instructions and guidance given in Figure 7. Attempting to complete the "merge" with 10,000 points (or a similarly high number) per SLIP as shown in Figure 7 resulted in the dashboard crashing. Other attempts to perform the analysis successfully ran during the initial "Start merging" but crashed when attempting to display the output as a density plot. Merging with the default 5,000 points per SLIP produced a similar but not identical density figure to that illustrated in Figure 7. For case study #3, it is appreciated that the authors provide a method to download the data and files needed to replicate the analysis.

The major issues that we see with replicability are that the method underlying the "Merge SLIP" analysis is not based on a peer-reviewed publication and that this thesis is not publicly available. While the results of the dashboard can be replicated using the code provided, there is no way to replicate the analysis independent of the underlying dashboard code.

Is sufficient information provided to allow interpretation of the expected output datasets and any results generated using the tool?

The dashboard 'filter' functionalities correctly filter the WALIS database (tested on our own inputs) and provide accessible summaries of the selected data in csv format (as described in use case #1). We feel that these are the most useful and robust outputs that the dashboard provides.

Importantly, we have concerns that the manuscript's suggested interpretation in use case #2 lacks important nuance for some users, including ambiguity about interpreting indicator elevations as "relative sea level". This may potentially mislead future researchers using the dashboard. Additionally, neither the dashboard nor the manuscript provide sufficient information to interpret the Merge SLIP point and density clouds. The lack of accessible, peer-reviewed literature supporting the Merge SLIP analysis prevents robust interpretation of the dashboard output, since the analysis itself has not been validated by the greater community and the literature needed for an individual researcher to closely examine the method is not publicly available.

Dashboard Functionality Comments

The aspect ratio of the world map on the 'Interactive map' tab does not allow the user to visualize the entire globe (viewed on both an iMac and laptop running Ubuntu), yet this is never specified. Both reviewers confused the 'extent:map' specification as meaning the entire globe. (This becomes clear to a user in the 'geographic extent' thumbnail in the Summary table tab. For example, at the maximum zoom out, to include all of North America in the default map almost none of South America can be included in the map). This matters because the corresponding 'sea level plot' then has an unspecified geographic filter. When we drag the map around--at the same zoom and with the filter saying 'extent:map' throughout--the 'sea level plot' updates with the map area, but at no point can we see the 'sea level plot' for the entire globe. It appears that a user can never view a sea level plot for the entire globe. We request that the default "Interactive map" be the full globe. We request that the 'extent:map' clarify whether the whole globe, or a subset of the globe is selected, and that any further sub-selection of the map area (by manual polygon versus zoom-in area) have a more specific filter label.

We would appreciate a 'Reset' button to return all filters to default ranges.

For Summary Table, can you clarify the meaning of 'blank' entries for the user? This may be clear to those who have uploaded data, but perhaps not to those who are coming with fresh eyes.

For the filter such as age range and elevation error, it would be beneficial to add an option to manually enter in the desired numeric range. While the sliders work well in some scenarios, for ranges spanning large numeric intervals (such as those in the age range), selecting specific values solely with the slider may be difficult or inaccessible to some users.

The dashboard crashes at times when developing a density cloud, particularly when high Point per SLIP values are used in the merging options.

Line-specific Comments

- Would benefit from copy-editing; grammatical errors introduce some ambiguity about the dashboard's function.

- Please clarify what you mean by 'database consists of multiple tables with one-to-one or many-to-many relationships' (page 3).
- Please clarify what you mean in the sentence 'In our design ... as proposed by 4'.
- The text states that the map visualization displays sea level indicators with pop-ups with additional metadata on elevation measurements and dating, etc.. (page 4), yet we find that this metadata only includes the indicator code (RSL_####) with no additional data as described. Please update the pop-up or this text accordingly.
- The authors state that the platform includes notes explaining the temporal and relative sea-level dimensions for each of the nine types of sea level indicators (page 5), though we could only find information on the temporal aspects when hovering our cursor over the nine symbols. Information about the sea-level meaning is missing.~
- The 'Merge SLIP' tab title (page 5) is jargon, please consider a phrase more understandable to the non-sea-level expert end user.
- Change 130.00 to 135.00 in restriction #2 of the numbered list in user case #1 (page 7).
- One page 7, the text for use case #1 reads "(e.g., 135 to 110 ka to include additional data)" when describing the age filter menu - please clarify whether this is a theoretical example or a part of the use case, as in order to replicate the sea level plot in figure 6, the age range had to be 135 - 110 kyr (as listed in the example filter diagram in figure 6), not the 130 - 115 kyr listed in item 2 of the restrictions for use case #2.
- For Figure 6a, you only specify the RSL filters 'elevation error' but not the 'percentile' and 'uncertainty'. Please specify the former to make this case study more easy to replicate.
- Please clarify what you mean by 'relative sea-level indicators can have more than one constraint' (page 8).
- Please clarify what you mean by 'Uniform distribution' in 'For example, sea level indicators in which the age calculation comes from a Uniform distribution from a Marine Isotope Stage (MIS) assignment' (page 8).
- Please clarify what you mean by 'remove individual sea-level indicators by code' (page 8).
- In Figure 1, please restructure elements of the figure to clarify the relationship between the WALIS database itself, the archived copy on Zenodo, the contributors, and the end users.
- We could not reproduce Figure 7 from the information in the text/figure. Please offer more information to replicate this case study.

Is the rationale for developing the new software tool clearly explained?

Yes

Is the description of the software tool technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of the code, methods and analysis (if applicable) provided to allow replication of the software development and its use by others?

Partly

Is sufficient information provided to allow interpretation of the expected output datasets and any results generated using the tool?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Stratigraphy, sea level.

We confirm that we have read this submission and believe that we have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however we have significant reservations, as outlined above.
